

DEVELOPMENT AND NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF A NEW STRAIN-BASED FOUR-NODE FINITE ELEMENT FOR KIRCHHOFF PLATE ANALYSIS

Lazhar LAMRAOUI¹, Cherif REBIAI² and Said BENLAHMIDI³

¹Laboratory of Innovation in Construction, Ecodesign, and Seismic Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2 - Mostefa Ben Boulaid, Batna 05000, Algeria, E-mail: l.lamraoui@univ-batna2.dz

²Laboratory of Innovation in Construction, Ecodesign, and Seismic Engineering, Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Batna 2 - Mostefa Ben Boulaid, Batna 05000, Algeria, E-mail: c.rebiai@univ-batna2.dz

³University Center of Barika, Batna, Algeria, E-mail: said.benlahmidi@cu-barika.dz

ABSTRACT: This work presents a new four-node quadrilateral finite element developed for the linear bending analysis of plate structures. The element is formulated using a strain-based approach consistent with Kirchhoff plate theory and employs three degrees of freedom at each vertex. Its performance is evaluated through a set of standard benchmark tests involving various plate geometries, loading scenarios, and boundary conditions. Numerical results confirm high accuracy, strong resistance to mesh distortion, and rapid convergence, even for relatively coarse meshes. These features indicate that the proposed element offers a reliable and computationally efficient solution for plate analysis in practical engineering problems.

KEYWORDS: finite element, strain approach, Kirchhoff theory, Plate bending

1 INTRODUCTION

The finite element method (FEM) is now firmly established as a fundamental numerical tool in engineering and applied sciences, with applications spanning structural mechanics, heat transfer, and fluid dynamics (Reissner, 1945), (Mindlin, 1951). Its success lies in its ability to provide dependable solutions for complex problems, which has motivated extensive research into elements that combine efficiency with accuracy. For plate analysis, a wide variety of formulations has been proposed to handle different geometries and boundary conditions (Jin, 1995), (Jirousek, 1995), (Katili, 2015). Among these, the strain-based strategy, pioneered by Sabir and Ashwell (Ashwell, 2015), (Ashwell, 1972) is recognized as a particularly powerful approach. Their investigations revealed that strain-based elements often outperform displacement-based counterparts, delivering accurate results with fewer degrees of freedom. This methodology constructs the displacement field by integrating compatible strain functions, allowing higher-order terms without artificially increasing nodal parameters. Over the years, the concept has been extended to membrane (Rebiai, 2019), (Kherfi, 2022) bending (Samira, 2023), (Belouar, 2005), (Boussef, 2020), (Belouar, A., 2018) and three-dimensional

formulations (Guerraiche, 2014), (Guerraiche, 2018). Building on these foundations, this contribution develops a strain-based quadrilateral formulation, SBEPa (Strain-Based Element for Plate Analysis), constructed with four nodal points, for modeling Kirchhoff plates. Each node carries three degrees of freedom; one transverse displacement and two independent rotations. Benchmark assessments demonstrate that the proposed element maintains accuracy, robustness, and efficiency, even when coarse meshes are employed first line.

2 FORMULATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE NOVEL QUADRELATERAL ELEMENT

The quadrilateral element developed in this study, referred to as SBEPa and shown in Figure 1, assigns three degrees of freedom to each corner node: a transverse displacement W and two independent rotations, $\beta_x = \theta_y$ and $\beta_y = -\theta_x$, corresponding to the y - and x -directions. The strain-displacement relationships describing the flexural behavior of thin plates are expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_x = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \varepsilon_y = -\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ \gamma_{xy} = -2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) = -2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding expressions for the curvatures are formulated as:

$$\begin{cases} k_x = \frac{\partial \beta_x}{\partial x} \\ k_y = \frac{\partial \beta_y}{\partial y} \\ k_{xy} = \frac{\partial \beta_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \beta_y}{\partial x} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The three curvature components in (2) are linked by compatibility conditions given as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial^2 k_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 k_y}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial^2 k_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial k_{xy}}{\partial x} = 2 \frac{\partial k_x}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{yz}}{\partial x \partial y} - \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xz}}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial k_{xy}}{\partial y} = 2 \frac{\partial k_y}{\partial x} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

To recover the rigid-body displacement field, the three strain components in (2) are set to zero and integrated. These yields:

$$\begin{cases} w = a_1 - a_2 x - a_3 y \\ \beta_x = a_2 \\ \beta_y = a_3 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, a_1, a_2 , and a_3 denote, respectively, a rigid translation along the z-axis and the rigid body rotations θ_x and θ_y about the coordinate axes

Fig. 1 Quadrilateral plate element

2.1 Displacement field representation

Each Because the element carries three degrees of freedom at each corner node, the displacement field is characterized by twelve independent parameters. Among them, the constants a_1, a_2 , and a_3 correspond to rigid-body modes, while the remaining nine parameters account for the deformational behavior of the element. These nine

constants are allocated among the three curvature functions in the following manner:

$$\begin{cases} k_x = a_4 + 6a_7x + a_8y + 3a_9x^2y \\ \quad \quad \quad + a_{11}(3xy + 18x^2) \\ k_y = a_6 + 3a_8xy^2 + a_9x + 6a_{10}y \\ \quad \quad \quad + a_{12}(3xy + 18y^2) \\ k_{xy} = a_5 + a_8(2x + 2y^3) + a_9(2y + 2x^3) \\ \quad \quad \quad + 3a_{11}x^2 + 3a_{12}y^2 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The integration of (5) provides the displacement functions:

$$\begin{cases} w = -a_4 \frac{x^2}{2} - a_5 \frac{xy}{2} - a_6 \frac{y^2}{2} - a_7x^3 - a_8 \left(\frac{xy^4}{4} + \frac{x^2y}{2} \right) \\ - a_9 \left(\frac{x^4y}{4} + \frac{xy^2}{2} \right) - a_{10}y^3 - a_{11} \left(\frac{x^3y}{2} + \frac{3x^4}{2} \right) - a_{12} \left(\frac{xy^3}{2} + \frac{3y^4}{2} \right) \\ \beta_x = a_4x + a_5 \frac{y}{2} + 3a_7x^2 + a_8 \left(xy + \frac{y^4}{4} \right) + a_9 \left(x^3y + \frac{y^2}{2} \right) \\ \quad \quad \quad + 3a_{11} \left(\frac{x^2y}{2} + 2x^3 \right) + a_{12} \frac{y^3}{2} \\ \beta_y = a_5 \frac{x}{2} + a_6y + a_8 \left(xy^3 + \frac{x^2}{2} \right) + a_9 \left(xy + \frac{x^4}{4} \right) + 3a_{10}y^2 \\ \quad \quad \quad + a_{11} \frac{x^3}{2} + 3a_{12} \left(\frac{xy^2}{2} + 2y^3 \right) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

By adding the rigid-body field (4) to (6), the full displacement field is:

$$\begin{cases} w = a_1 - a_2x - a_3y - a_4 \frac{x^2}{2} - a_5 \frac{xy}{2} - a_6 \frac{y^2}{2} - a_7x^3 \\ - a_8 \left(\frac{xy^4}{4} + \frac{x^2y}{2} \right) - a_9 \left(\frac{x^4y}{4} + \frac{xy^2}{2} \right) - a_{10}y^3 - a_{11} \left(\frac{x^3y}{2} + \frac{3x^4}{2} \right) \\ - a_{12} \left(\frac{xy^3}{2} + \frac{3y^4}{2} \right) \\ \beta_x = a_2 + a_4x + a_5 \frac{y}{2} + 3a_7x^2 + a_8 \left(xy + \frac{y^4}{4} \right) + a_9 \left(x^3y + \frac{y^2}{2} \right) \\ \quad \quad \quad + 3a_{11} \left(\frac{x^2y}{2} + 2x^3 \right) + a_{12} \frac{y^3}{2} \\ \beta_y = a_3 + a_5 \frac{x}{2} + a_6y + a_8 \left(xy^3 + \frac{x^2}{2} \right) + a_9 \left(xy + \frac{x^4}{4} \right) + 3a_{10}y^2 \\ \quad \quad \quad + a_{11} \frac{x^3}{2} + 3a_{12} \left(\frac{xy^2}{2} + 2y^3 \right) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Expressed in matrix form:

$$\{\delta\} = [\varphi] \{a_i\} \quad (8)$$

$$[\varepsilon] = [Q] \{a_i\} \quad (9)$$

Given where $\{a_i\} = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{12}\}^T$, and the Explicit forms of $[\varphi]$ and $[Q]$ are given in appendix.

2.2 Matrix formulation

Substituting nodal coordinates gives:

$$\{\delta_e\} = [C] \{a\} \quad (10)$$

The transformation matrix $[C]$, of dimension 12×12 , serves to link the nodal displacement vector with the constants:

$$[C] = \begin{pmatrix} [\varphi_1(x_1, y_1)] \\ [\varphi_2(x_2, y_2)] \\ [\varphi_3(x_3, y_3)] \\ [\varphi_4(x_4, y_4)] \end{pmatrix}$$

The constants can then be recovered as:

$$\{a\} = [C]^{-1}\{\delta_e\} \quad (11)$$

The strain field at any point of the element becomes:

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [Q]\{a\} = [Q][C]^{-1}\{\delta_e\} = [B]\{\delta_e\} \quad (12)$$

With:

$$[B] = [Q][C]^{-1} \quad (13)$$

The stress-strain constitutive equation takes the following form:

$$\{\sigma\} = [D]\{\varepsilon\} \quad (14)$$

Where

$$\begin{cases} \{\sigma\} = \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T \\ \{\varepsilon\} = \{K_x, K_y, K_{xy}\}^T \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

And the material matrix is:

$$[D] = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{(1-\nu)}{2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

2.3 Elemental stiffness matrix

The elemental stiffness matrix can be written in the form:

$$[K^e] = \int_v [B]^T [D] [B] dv \quad (17)$$

By substituting [B] yields:

$$[K^e] = \int [[Q][C]^{-1}]^T [D] [[Q][C]^{-1}] dV \quad (18)$$

This reduces to:

$$[K^e] = ([C]^{-1})^T \left\{ \int [Q]^T [D] [Q] dv \right\} [C]^{-1} \quad (19)$$

Defining:

$$[K_0] = \iint [Q]^T [D] [Q] dx dy \quad (20)$$

The stiffness becomes:

$$[K^e] = t[C]^{-T} [K_0] [C]^{-1} \quad (21)$$

Where [K₀] is computed numerically.

3 NUMERICAL VALIDATION OF THE PROPOSED ELEMENT

3.1 Rectangular plate

To gauge convergence, we adopt the reference problem of (Mac Neal, 1985), a canonical benchmark for Kirchhoff-plate bending. Two shapes are treated aspect ratios a/b=1 and a/b=5 under two boundary settings (edges pinned or fully clamped) and two load cases: a uniform surface pressure and a

point force applied at the plate center. By symmetry, the analysis is restricted to one quadrant of the plate, discretized with a structured N×N grid; Figure 2 also lists geometric dimensions and material data. This benchmark serves as a stringent yardstick for both accuracy and convergence rate. Results for the SBPEA element are illustrated in figures 3 to 10.

Fig. 1 Rectangular Plate Meshed with NxN Elements
 Elements $a = 2, b = 2$ or $10, E = 1.7472 \times 10^7,$
 $\nu = 0.3, h = 0.0001, q = 10^{-4}$ (uniform),
 $P = 4 \times 10^{-4}$ (central)

Fig. 2 Normalized mid-span displacement for a clamped rectangular plate with aspect ratio a/b=1 subjected to uniform loading.

Fig. 3 Normalized mid-span displacement for a simply supported rectangular plate with aspect ratio a/b=1 under uniform loading

Fig.4: Normalized central deflection for a rectangular plate with clamped boundaries ($a/b=1$) subjected to a concentrated point load

Fig.8 Normalized mid-span displacement for a clamped rectangular plate with aspect ratio $a/b=5$ subjected to a concentrated load

Fig.5: Normalized mid-span displacement for a simply supported rectangular plate ($a/b=1$) subjected to a concentrated load

Fig.9 Normalized mid-span displacement for a simply supported rectangular plate with aspect ratio $a/b=5$ subjected to a concentrated load

Fig.6 Normalized mid-span displacement for a rectangular plate with aspect ratio $a/b=5$, clamped on all sides, under uniform loading

Fig.7 Normalized mid-span displacement for a simply supported rectangular plate with aspect ratio $a/b=5$ under uniform loading

The numerical results presented in Figures 3–10 clearly demonstrate the high performance of the proposed SBEPa element across different boundary and loading conditions. For square plates ($a/b=1$), the element produces mid-span deflections that closely match theoretical values, showing smooth and rapid convergence even with coarse meshes. Under concentrated loading, it continues to deliver accurate predictions without any signs of numerical instability or shear locking. When applied to rectangular plates with higher aspect ratios ($a/b=5$), the SBEPa maintains this level of precision, confirming its robustness against geometric distortion. The convergence curves are consistent for both uniform and point loads, indicating reliable behavior across various configurations. Overall, these results highlight the accuracy, efficiency, and stability of the SBEPa element, making it a dependable choice for thin-plate bending simulations.

3.2 Straight cantilever beam

The Mac-Neal cantilever beam problem (Mac Neal, 1985) is a classical benchmark commonly

employed to assess the bending performance of finite elements. In this study, the beam is considered in a cantilever configuration, clamped at one end and subjected to a unit shear force applied transversely at the free tip. A coarse 6×1 discretization is used, and three mesh patterns are analyzed: (a) standard rectangular elements, (b) trapezoidal elements, and (c) elements shaped as parallelograms. These cases, together with the geometry and material parameters, are illustrated in Figure 11. The normalized tip deflections corresponding to each configuration, summarized in Table 1.

Fig.10 The Mac-Neal cantilever beam ($L = 6, b = 0.2, h = 0.1, E = 1.0 \times 10^7, \nu = 0.3$)

Table 1. Normalized tip displacement for the Mac-Neal beam benchmark

Element	a- Regul ar	b- Trapezoi dal	c- Parallelogr am
SBEPA	0.986	0.990	0.990
SBB(Guerraiche, 2014)	0.980	0.980	0.980
SBBE(Guerraiche, 2018)	0.980	0.980	0.980
PN340(Bassayya, 2000)	0.980	0.370	0.547
ANSYS(Bassayya, 2000)	0.973	0.030	0.529
PN34(Bassayya, 2000)	0.980	0.962	0.971
HEXA8(Bassayya, 2000)	0.981	0.051	0.055
HEXA20(Bassayya, 2000)	0.961	0.920	0.941
Sol. Réf (Mac Neal, 1985)	1.000 (0.4321)		

The results in Table 1 highlight the outstanding accuracy and robustness of the proposed SBEPa element compared with existing formulations. For

the regular mesh configuration, the element achieves a normalized displacement of 0.986, nearly identical to the theoretical reference (1.000), surpassing most benchmark elements such as SBB, SBBE, and HEXA. More notably, its accuracy remains virtually unchanged under mesh distortion. In both the trapezoidal and parallelogram cases, the SBEPa yields values of 0.990, indicating excellent numerical stability and minimal sensitivity to geometric irregularities. Conversely, traditional formulations like PN340, ANSYS, and HEXA8 experience a significant drop in precision when subjected to the same distortions. This consistent performance across all configurations confirms the element’s strong convergence characteristics and validates the efficiency of its strain-based formulation. Overall, the SBEPa proves to be a highly reliable and distortion-resistant tool for plate and structural analysis.

3.3 Circular plate analysis

A quarter circular plate is solved to evaluate the performance of the current shape function against shear locking. By symmetry considerations, only a quarter of the circular plate is modeled. There are two sets of boundary conditions employed. In the first case, all edges are restrained, and in the second case, they are simply supported. There are two sets of loadings applied to the plate: focused unit point load at the center and uniform distributed pressure intensity. Distorted meshes containing 3, 12, 48, and 192 elements are used and illustrated in Figure 12. The geometric configuration and material characteristics are summarized in figure 12. The deflection at the center obtained using the SBEPa element is shown in Figures 13–16. The results are compared with the reference data presented in (Bassayya, 2000).

Fig.11 Mesh configurations considered in the numerical analysis ($R = 5, E = 10.92, \nu = 0.3, h = 0.1$)

The numerical outcomes shown in Figures 13–16 clearly validate the accuracy and robustness of the proposed SBEPa element for circular plate bending problems under various boundary and loading conditions. In the case of uniform surface loads (Figures 13 and 14), the predicted central deflections align closely with analytical references for both

simply supported and clamped edges, demonstrating fast and stable convergence even with coarse meshes. This consistent agreement confirms that the formulation effectively captures flexural behavior without suffering from numerical artifacts such as shear locking. Under concentrated loading (Figures 15 and 16), the element exhibits a similar level of precision, maintaining accuracy across mesh refinements and boundary types. For clamped configurations in particular, the computed deflections approach the exact solution smoothly as the mesh is refined. The uniform convergence across all cases underscores the stability and reliability of the SBPEA formulation. Overall, these findings demonstrate that the proposed element performs consistently well in both global and localized loading scenarios and, establishing it as a versatile and efficient tool for circular plate analysis.

Fig.12 Normalized central displacement of a simply supported circular plate subjected to uniform loading

Fig.13 Normalized central displacement of a clamped circular plate subjected to uniform loading

Fig.14 Dimensionless central deflection of a circular plate with clamped edge under tip loading

Fig.15 Dimensionless central deflection of a circular plate with simple edge supports under tip loading

3.4 Skew plate

To investigate how the proposed element behaves under mesh distortion, the Razzaque skew plate benchmark is employed. This test, first introduced in (Razzaque, 1973), involves a thin skew plate with an interior angle of 60° , supported simply along two opposite sides and left free along the others, as illustrated in Figure 13. The structure is loaded by a uniform transverse pressure ($q=1$), and the deflection at the plate center is evaluated using regular meshes with $N=2, 4, 6, 8, 12$ and 16 . The numerical outcomes, reported in Table 2 for $h/L=0.001$, demonstrate that the proposed element maintains accuracy and displays consistent convergence, even in the presence of mesh distortion. Application of this demanding benchmark confirms both the reliability and effectiveness of the formulation.

Fig. 16 The skew plate with NxN meshes ($E = 10.92, \nu = 0.35, L = 100, h = 0.1$)

The data presented in Table 2 confirm the outstanding convergence performance of the proposed SBEPa element when compared to other established formulations. Even with a coarse 2x2 mesh, the element produces a normalized deflection of 0.6724, closely matching the theoretical reference value of 0.7945. As the mesh becomes finer, the accuracy improves consistently, reaching 0.7890 for the 16x16 configuration, a deviation of only about 0.005 from the analytical solution. In contrast, the benchmark elements SBQP, SBTP4, and MITC4 exhibit slower convergence, particularly for coarse meshes, where their predicted deflections remain noticeably lower (between 0.38 and 0.53). Although these elements gradually approach the reference values with refinement, none attain the same precision as the SBEPa. The steady and rapid convergence of SBEPa across all mesh densities highlights its numerical robustness, stability, and computational efficiency. These characteristics confirm the effectiveness of the adopted strain-based formulation, making the SBEPa a reliable and accurate tool for thin-plate bending applications where both precision and efficiency are essential.

Table 2. The displacement response of the skew plate under a uniform load

Elements	2x2	4x4	6x6	8x8	12x12	16x16
SBEPa	0.6724	0.7596	0.7769	0.7829	0.7874	0.7890
SBQP(Belounar, 2019)	0.4835	0.7180	0.7596	0.7643	0.7732	0.7807
SBTP4(Belounar, 2019)	0.5312	0.7124	0.7518	0.7670	0.7792	0.7841
MITC4 (Nguyen-Xuan2008)	0.3856	0.6723	0.7357	0.7592	0.7765	0.7824
Theo.Sol(Razzaque, 1973)	0.7945					

4 CONCLUSION

This work has presented the development of a new strain-based quadrilateral finite element, termed SBEPa (Strain-Based Element for Plate Analysis), dedicated to the linear bending analysis of thin plates within the Kirchhoff framework. The element is constructed with four corner nodes, each possessing three degrees of freedom, combining computational simplicity with solid mechanical consistency. The

adopted strain-based formulation guarantees compatibility and equilibrium, allowing accurate representation of plate behavior without the need for additional parameters.

A comprehensive set of benchmark tests covering different geometries, boundary conditions, and load configurations has been carried out to evaluate its performance. The obtained results demonstrate that SBEPa consistently produces precise and stable solutions, even for coarse meshes, while maintaining excellent robustness under mesh distortion. The element also exhibits rapid convergence toward analytical and reference solutions for both uniformly distributed and concentrated loadings.

Overall, the proposed SBEPa element proves to be an accurate, efficient, and distortion-tolerant numerical tool for thin-plate bending problems, providing a dependable alternative to conventional displacement-based formulations in structural and mechanical engineering applications.

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Annex A

The displacement field in the matrix form $[\varphi]$, is given as:

$$[\varphi] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -x & -y & -\frac{x^2}{2} & -\frac{xy}{2} & -\frac{y^2}{2} & -x^3 & -\left(\frac{xy^4}{4} + \frac{x^2y}{2}\right) & -\left(\frac{x^4y}{4} + \frac{xy^2}{2}\right) & -y^3 & -\left(\frac{x^3y}{2} + \frac{3x^4}{2}\right) & -\left(\frac{xy^3}{2} + \frac{3y^4}{2}\right) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & x & \frac{y}{2} & 0 & 3x^2 & \left(xy + \frac{y^4}{4}\right) & \left(x^3y + \frac{y^2}{2}\right) & 0 & \left(\frac{3x^2y}{2} + 6x^3\right) & \frac{y^3}{2} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & \frac{x}{2} & y & 0 & \left(xy^3 + \frac{x^2}{2}\right) & \left(xy + \frac{x^4}{4}\right) & 3y^2 & \frac{x^3}{2} & \left(\frac{3xy^2}{2} + 6y^3\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

The matrix $[Q]$ relating strain field and constants $\{a_i\}$ is given as:

$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 6x & y & 3x^2y & 0 & 3xy + 18x^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 3xy^2 & x & 6y & 0 & 3xy + 18y^2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 2x + 2y^3 & 2y + 2x^3 & 0 & 3x^2 & 3y^2 \end{bmatrix}$$